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Data Review

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Abstract

This data review examines the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES) Integrated Module Dataset (IMD), a large cross-national survey covering voting behavior and political attitudes across dozens of countries since the mid-1990s. Among the project's key substantive themes are voter choice, ideological self-placement, and evaluations of political actors. The coverage of post-Soviet and Baltic states in the dataset is uneven, with greater representation of the Baltic states; this limits longitudinal analysis for cases such as Russia and Ukraine. Finally, the review outlines the dataset's main methodological features and limitations, including cross-national differences in survey implementation and potential biases related to social desirability and political context, such as fear-driven responses. The data can be downloaded for free, although registration on the GESIS portal is required.

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Review of the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems

The Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES) Integrated Module Dataset (IMD) is a large-scale cross-national survey dataset aimed to be used for cross-country research on voting behavior and political attitudes. The CSES project was founded and became operational in mid-1990s. The project is based on cooperation among national election study teams. The collected data get merged with demographic (age, gender, education, income, occupation, place of residence). The resulting datasets are publicly available for download through GESIS, although registration is required.

The project is organized into temporal modules. Each of the modules covers roughly a five-year period. The IMD includes CSES Modules 1-5 (mid-1990s until 2021) and contains data from over 200 election studies, conducted in 59 polities. The sixth CSES module covers 2021-2026 and is currently ongoing. Accordingly, it is currently not included in the IMD. Information on Module 6 is available here: <https://cses.org/data-download/cses-module-6-2021-2026/>.

As for the post-Soviet region and the Baltic states, their coverage in the dataset is as follows:

- Module 1 (1996–2002): Belarus (2001), Lithuania (1997), Russia (1999, 2000), Ukraine (1998).
- Module 2 (2001–2006): Kyrgyzstan (2005), Russia (2004).
- Module 3 (2005–2011): Belarus (2008), Estonia (2011), Latvia (2010).
- Module 4 (2011–2016): Latvia (2011, 2014).
- Module 5 (2015–2021): Latvia (2018), Lithuania (2016, 2020).

Substantively, the IMD covers the questions related to voting behavior and political attitudes. Core topics include (but not limited to): voter choice, party identification, ideological self-placement, evaluation of parties and leaders, satisfaction with democracy. As noted above, the IMD also provides basic demographic information about respondents. In addition, the dataset includes some macro-level characteristics, such as features of a country's electoral system and political institutions.

In national studies, the target population consists of eligible voters in national elections. Surveys are typically conducted post-election by election study teams using representative samples. Sampling procedures vary across countries and studies, and survey modes include primarily face-to-face interviews, as well as telephone, mail-back, and mixed-mode approaches.

A key feature of the IMD is harmonization. Variables from different CSES modules are recoded to enhance comparability over time. The dataset also harmonizes identifiers for parties and

coalitions, enabling researchers to track support for and perceptions of political actors across modules.

Several limitations of the dataset should also be noted. First, despite harmonization, differences in survey implementation, sampling approaches, and question placement across countries and modules may limit comparability. Second, data quality may be affected by recall error—a common issue in post-election surveys—as well as by social desirability bias and, in less democratic polities, fear-related response bias. Third, coverage of the post-Soviet region and the Baltic states is uneven: some countries appear only once or a few times in the dataset (see above), which complicates or precludes longitudinal analysis for these cases.

Related publications:

- Howell, D. A. (2010). “Enhancing quality and comparability in the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES).” In *Survey Methods in Multinational, Multiregional, and Multicultural Contexts*, pp. 525–534.
- McAllister, I. (2008). "Public support for democracy: Results from the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems project." *Electoral Studies* 27(1), 1-4.
- Quinlan, S., C. Schimpf, K. Blinzler, and S. Živković (2024). “Harmonization in the Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES) Projects.” In *Survey Data Harmonization in the Social Sciences*, pp. 89–106.